

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Estimating Protistan Diversity using High-throughput Sequencing by Sarah K. Hu, Zhenfeng Liu, Alle A. Y. Lie, Peter D. Countway, Diane Y. Kim, Adriane C. Jones, Rebecca J. Gast, S. Craig Cary, Evelyn B. Sherr, Barry F. Sherr & David A. Caron

Fig. S1. Comparison of nmMDS plots of full-length and *in silico* extracted regions. Non-metric Multidimensional Scaling (nmMDS) plots of the Bray-Curtis dissimilarity parameter based on OTUs called at 97% sequence similarity. nmMDS plots and Bray-Curtis dissimilarity values for full-length sequences and extracted regions were generated in Primer Ev. 6 (Clark and Warwick 2001). Similarity overlays represent 10% (solid black lines), 20% (dashed black lines), and 40% community similarity (solid grey lines). Each sample is labeled by a location and depth identifier (e.g. AO500: Arctic Ocean, 500 m), Arctic Ocean (AO), the San Pedro Ocean time series station in the eastern North Pacific (ENP), East Pacific Rise (EPR) in the eastern Pacific, Gulf Stream (GS) in the western North Atlantic, and Ross Sea, Antarctica (RS), see Table S2. The pattern of the MDS for the V7 region (A) was not consistent (lacked the resolving power) with MDS plots for the V4 (B), V1-V3 (C), V1-V4 (D), V4-V7 (E), V1-V7 (F), and full-length sequences (G). In contrast, MDS plots of the datasets consisting of sequences ≥ 400 nt yielded patterns that were generally consistent with one another (B-F). Only minor differences (e.g. the grouping of the Ross Sea samples, and some North Pacific and North Atlantic samples) were apparent among the patterns generated by longer sequences (B-F).

Table S1. Summary of mean nucleotide (nt) length of each sequence fragment used, along with forward and reverse primer and reference position on the 18S rRNA gene used for *in silico* extraction. Position reference refers to the nucleotide position in the aligned full-length 18S rRNA gene sequence database. Fragment lengths reported include the primer sequences. The V1-V3 and V4 regions overlap along the 18S rRNA gene. Primers chosen represent commonly used primers for sequencing environmental microbial eukaryotic communities and therefore serve to provide realistic examples of short fragments that would be used in HTS.

Region ID	Mean length (nt)	Primer sequence (5'-3'):		Position Reference	Primer reference
		Forward	Reverse		
V7	107	AAT TTG ACT CAA CAC GGG		3,324	Hadziavdic et al. (2014)
		ACT AAG AAC GGC CAT GCA CC		3,518	
V4	418	CCA GCA [GC]C [CT]G CGG TAA TTC C		1,141	Stoeck et al. (2010)
		ACT TTC GTT CTT GAT [CT][GA]A		1,593	
V1-V3	533	AAC CTG GTT GAT CCT GCC AGT		0	Medlin et al. (1988)
		GTA ATT CCA GCT CCA ATA GC □		1,213	Weekers et al. (1994)
V1-V4	690	AAC CTG GTT GAT CCT GCC AGT		0	Medlin et al. (1988)
		CCA GCA [GC]C [CT]G CGG TAA TTC C		1,593	Stoeck et al. (2010)
V4-V7	1,200	CCA GCA [GC]C [CT]G CGG TAA TTC C		1,141	Stoeck et al. (2010)
		ACT AAG AAC GGC CAT GCA CC		3,518	Hadziavdic et al. (2014)
V1-V7	1,260	AAC CTG GTT GAT CCT GCC AGT		0	Medlin et al. (1988)
		ACT AAG AAC GGC CAT GCA CC		3,518	Hadziavdic et al. (2014)
Full-length	1,647	AAC CTG GTT GAT CCT GCC AGT			Medlin et al. (1988)
		TGA TCC TTC TGC AGG TTC ACC TAC			

Table S2. Summary of sampling dates, coordinates, depth, and number of quality checked sequences recovered from each sample.

Samples	Abbrev.	Date of collection	Latitude	Longitude	Depth (meters)	Sequences per sample
Ross Sea	RS	11/14/05	76.04 S	170.30 E	20	654
					600	694
Arctic Ocean	AO	8/12/02 8/11/02	73.42 N	157.40 W	35	729
					500	857
Eastern North Pacific	ENP	10/29/01	33.55 N	118.40 W	5	592
					500	339
East Pacific Rise	EPR	12/8/03	9.84 N	104.35 W	20	441
					1,500	848
					2,500	675
Gulf Stream	GS	8/24/00	34.73 N	73.95 W	15	471
					105	500
					2,500	632